

Organizational career growth: The mediating role of career management practices.

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Organizational career growth - the mediating role of career management practices

Abstract

The main objective of the study was to investigate the mediating role of career management practices (CMPs) in the relationship between firm characteristics, individual characteristics, hierarchical career plateau and organizational career growth. The study took a context-dependent approach by investigating the above in medium-sized enterprises of a developing country, Sri Lanka. The data were collected from 667 employees, those who are in supervisory or above level but not an owner, partner, or a member of family of owners/partners of medium-sized enterprises. Analysis of direct effects implied that CMPs driven by both organizations and employees have positive effect on organizational career growth. Age, the level of education attainment and the experience of hierarchical career plateau have significant effect on organizational career growth through CMPs driven by employees.

Keywords: organizational career growth, career management practices, hierarchical career plateau, medium-sized enterprises.

Introduction

Once the ideal career looked like lifetime job security with hierarchical advancement along with salary raises in exchange for hard work and loyalty (Reitman and Schneer 2008). However, due to changes in organizational restructuring and many other changes in wider social spheres employees are experiencing non-traditional careers where the focus is on continuous learning and psychological aspects of career success (see Ashraf 2019; Chen et al., 2016; Karavardar 2014; Spurk et al., 2019; Sullivan and Arthur 2006). Employees are no longer tied to a single organization. They experience job mobility with upward, lateral or downward moves involving changes in employer, geographic location, and even occupations in the 24/7 economy being available to the employer outside of the official work hours, perhaps working in various time zones around the world (Reitman and Schneer 2008). Hence, non-traditional career is dynamic and transitional in multiple organizations and occupations,

sometimes experiencing interruptions in employment. Non-traditional career can therefore be identified as self-directed by employees in contrast to traditional career, which is owned by the organizations.

Still, non-traditional career involves links between the organization and employees in a less structured or less permanent way (Baruch 2006; Karavardar 2014; Sullivan and Arthur 2006; Van de Griek et al. 2018; Weer and Greenhaus 2017). As argued by Glaser (2010), organizations obtain services from employees by offering some kind of career within the structure and distributing financial and non-financial rewards in accordance with the career level in return for their dedicated service. If an organization decides not to develop a career for its employees to the benefit of some other organization, retaining talent would become an important issue (Baruch 1999). Hence, managing employees' careers lies with both employees and organizations. For example, Baruch (2006) states "... current organizations are less rigid, but not fully fluid; control may not be solely with the organization, but the shift does not mean that the organization has no say in career management; individuals take more control of their own career, but much remains for organizations to manage ..." (p. 125). Practices that fulfill employees' expectations for career can, therefore, be considered as properties of the organizational career. When the current employing organization failed to provide desirable practices fulfilling employees' expectations for career, on the one hand, employees may decide to take the control and their core values operate as driving forces of career decisions, which Hall (2004) identified as self-initiation of career direction (p. 3). On the other hand, employees may decide to leave the current employing organization for better prospects elsewhere choosing to work for organizations that provide desirable conditions fulfilling their expectations (Chen et al. 2016; Karavardar 2014; Kohlmeyer III et al. 2017; Reitman and Schneer 2008). This implies that when employees perceive their current employing organization invests in their careers, they respond positively and generate positive impact for the organization. In this context, Reitman and Schneer (2008, p. 26) state "organizations would want employees to find that their greatest opportunities lie inside the company, not elsewhere". Accordingly, CMPs driven by employees that are reflective of

their personal career interests as well as CMPs driven by the organizations that are based on organizational needs could be witnessed at a particular point of time.

By identifying organizational career growth as employees' experience of career growth within their current organizations (Lyness and Thomson 2000; McElroy and Weng 2016; Spagnoli 2017), the present study investigated organizational career growth in medium-sized enterprises in Sri Lanka. The specific objectives of the study were to investigate whether (1) individual demographic characteristics, firm characteristics and the experience of hierarchical career plateau influence organizational career growth of employees engaged in medium sized-enterprises, (2) organizational career management practices (OCMPs) that are planned and implemented by organizations and individual career management practices (ICMPs) that are self-initiated by employees influence organizational career growth, and (3) CMPs mediate between individual demographic/firm characteristics and the experience of hierarchical career plateau and organizational career growth of employees engaged in medium sized-enterprises. The model (refer to Figure 1) and hypotheses proposed in the study to test the mediation are summarized in the next sub-section for clarity.

We tried to bridge the gap in the literature in several spheres. First, although a considerable progress has been made in advancing the knowledge on organizational career growth, scholars have called for more context-dependent investigations across countries, organizations, occupations and individuals' demographic characteristics (Chen et al. 2016; McElroy and Weng 2016; Pandya 2017; Van Osch and Schaveling 2017; Windels and Mallia 2015). Second, although small and medium enterprises (SMEs), in general, have a desire to pursue long-term strategic changes to be resilient and sustainable in the contemporary business world, the size of SMEs influences their capacity (Storey 2002; Wijetunge 2014). For example, Storey (2002, p. 250) stated "smaller enterprises are not 'scaled-down' versions of large enterprises. Small and large enterprises are equally distinctive". With regard to the management of human resources, labour market imperfections enable enterprises to earn rents on employees' capabilities. Still, the size of SMEs influences their capacity to adopt appropriate human resource management (HRM) practices. For example, Razouk (2011)

suggested that SMEs may lack capabilities to develop HRM practices but are more likely to adopt them to be sustainable and competitive. In this regard, medium sized-enterprises are in a better position than small ones in adopting appropriate HRM practices to recruit, motivate and retain employees. Therefore, mixing data across the enterprises of different size can distort research results; this implies the need of being specific on the size of enterprises being investigated. Since relatively a fewer number of empirical studies have been conducted on career management in medium-sized enterprises, relatively little is understood although this area remains an important topic of investigation among organizational researchers and practitioners.

Third, our context of the study tries to address a gap in the literature by examining organizational career growth in medium sized-enterprises operating in a developing country context. Micro-, small- and medium-sized enterprises play a vital role in the socio-economic development of any country ensuring that development is inclusive and balanced. These enterprises contribute to a major share in Gross Domestic Product, value-added output, the utilization of local factors of production, employment creation, export growth and have potential for equitable distribution of income. As a consequence, the SMEs sector has a close association with the performance of a nation. Despite these contributions, SMEs face resource constraints of time, money and human capital, which create enormous challenges in becoming resilient and sustainable in the contemporary business world. Therefore, academics and practitioners in the field of careers will be interested in understanding organizational career growth in medium sized-enterprises operating in a developing country to gain valuable information for research and policy making. In the review of literature, the term SMEs, in general, is used to refer to the combined category of micro-, small- and medium-sized enterprises. Specific reference is made to medium-sized enterprises as and when information is available.

Proposed model and hypotheses. Figure 1 shows the model proposed in the study. Based on the model, eight hypotheses are proposed as follows. In the next section, the literature is reviewed to support our arguments proposed in the Figure 1 and hypotheses.

Figure 1

- H1: Employees' experiences of OCMPs positively predict their organizational career growth.
- H2: Employees' experiences of ICMPs positively predict their organizational career growth.
- H3: Age, gender and the level of education attainment of employees predict CMPs experienced by them, where age is significantly positively associated with experiencing CMPs, males are experiencing CMPs significantly more than females, and employees with higher levels of educational attainment are experiencing CMPs significantly more than their counterparts at lower levels.
- H4: Age, gender and the level of education attainment of employees predict their organizational career growth, where age is significantly positively associated with experiencing organizational career growth, males are experiencing organizational career growth significantly more than their female counterparts, and employees with higher levels of educational attainment are experiencing organizational career growth more than their counterparts at lower levels.
- H5: Employees who are not hierarchically career plateaued utilize CMPs more than their counterparts whose length of time in the present position has been prolonged (i.e., experiencing hierarchical career plateau).
- H6: Employees who are not hierarchically career plateaued may experience organizational career growth more than their counterparts whose length of time in the present position has been prolonged.
- H7: Firm age (the duration of business operation) positively predicts employees' experiences of CMPs.
- H8: Firm age positively predicts the provision of avenues for employees' organizational career growth.

Literature review

Organizational career growth

Organizational career growth is defined as the degree to which employees experience career growth within their current organizations (McElroy and Weng 2016, p. 3-4). It provides a better understanding of whether organizations create an environment for employees to meet their career-related expectations and whether employees' accomplishments are reinforced by distributing financial and non-financial rewards. Accordingly, we review the literature with the expectation that organizational career growth directly associates with individuals' organizational attitudes and behaviors, and expresses employee–employer relationship in their current employing organization. Still, employees' experiences of organizational career growth may influence their career success, life well-being and even future career prospects.

Although traditional considerations of organizational career growth in terms of hierarchical progression and increases in salary have decreased its attractiveness with organizational restructuring, these two traditional proxies are still identified as primacy in capturing organizational career growth (Lyness and Thomson 2000; McElroy and Weng 2016). However, over the passage of time, proxies used to assess organizational career growth has been widened by incorporating dimensions such as challenging work, travel, flexibility, contribution, autonomy, and the degree to which work assignments and job opportunities match with one's career interests and goals (Chen et al. 2016; Karavardar 2014; Kraimer et al. 2011; Reitman and Schneer 2008; Spagnoli 2017; Weer and Greenhaus 2017).

Career management practices

Career management involves processes that can be used to develop employees' awareness about career opportunities available within the current organization, help them to set realistic career goals and implement CMPs to facilitate the achievement of career expectations. On the one hand, CMPs increase options available for organizations to achieve business objectives by ensuring the availability of employees who are committed and loyal to the organization due to career development avenues made available to them (Baruch 1999, 2006). On the other hand, CMPs allow individuals to develop a structure, direction, meaning and purpose to

their organizational roles. For example, Bagdadli and Gianecchini (2019) suggest types of mechanisms, namely developmental, informational, and relational that could justify organizational investments in career management, which will translate into individual career success. Therefore, CMPs ensure organized working environment in which employees are able to achieve their career expectations. Accordingly, CMPs describe practices which may decrease the time required for and uncertainty surrounding the attainment of career expectations. Hence, CMPs acquire an important place in career management, and involve efforts taken by both employees and organizations (Ashraf 2019; Kohlmeyer III et al. 2017; Van de Griek et al. 2018). While organizational career management practices (OCMPs) are planned and implemented by the organization with the intention of managing careers of its employees, individual career management practices (ICMPs) are self-directed actions of employees to manage their own careers.

Organizational career management practices. Organizational CMPs aim to satisfy the needs of both organizations and employees and involve a wide range of practices (Ashraf 2019; Huang et al. 2017; Karavardar 2014; Kohlmeyer III et al. 2017; Pandya 2017; Reitman and Schneer 2008; Spagnoli 2017; Weer and Greenhaus 2017; Wang et al. 2014; Weng and McElroy 2012). Even in the context of non-traditional careers, OCMPs constitute a central part of HRM to respond to changing requirements in a competent and flexible way (Lips-Wiersma and Hall 2007; Nawaz and Pangil 2016). Some of the OCMPs include but not limited to job posting, filling vacancies from within policies, providing training and development programmes, carrying out performance and potential appraisals, and maintaining career paths for hierarchical and/or cross-functional mobility (Baruch 2006; Baruch and Peiperl 2000; Eby et al. 2005; Nouri and Parker 2013; Wang et al. 2014; Weng and McElroy 2012).

Small and medium enterprises pay lower financial and non-financial rewards for employees due to lower productivity and profits compared to larger enterprises; these enterprises are less likely to maintain internal labour market and are very unlikely to manage the careers of employees. As a result, smaller enterprises are less likely to obtain rents from employees and employees may seek better job prospects elsewhere. However, smaller

enterprises may place a premium on immediate returns from human resources considering the uncertainty in their business environment with compared to larger enterprises. Therefore, smaller enterprises may still adopt some practices such as training on new procedures as long as the market for these procedures is certain (Storey 2002). Although mostly ad hoc and reactive, SMEs facilitate apprentice training, supplier sponsored training, trade association organized training, or training required by regulatory bodies or larger customers (Johnson 2002). In other words, SMEs may address problems that they perceive as the most dominant ones confronting them, which best predicts success or failure of the enterprise with the use of human resources.

With regard to specific OCMPs used in medium-sized enterprises, Singh and Vohra (2009) found that a higher percentage of medium-sized enterprises involved in HR planning, job analysis and maintaining written job descriptions compared to small-sized enterprises. Singh and Vohra (2009) and Storey (2002) showed that medium-sized enterprises involved more in the provision of training or financial support for training than small-sized enterprises. Wickramasinghe (2016) and Singh and Vohra (2009) showed that medium-sized enterprises involved in appraising performance of employees' and these results are used as a basis for decisions on salary increments.

Overall, based on the above reviewed literature, SMEs are more likely to adopt an opportunistic behavior and strategically choose and provide OCMPs to best utilize human resources for the best impact. By doing so, SMEs may wish to maintain that employees find opportunities to meet their career expectations lie inside the enterprise, which discourage them leaving for better prospects elsewhere (see Chen et al. 2016; Nawaz and Pangil 2016). Although few studies suggested an association between OCMPs and employees' career-related expectations (e.g., Lips-Wiersma and Hall 2007; Nouri and Parker 2013; Wang et al. 2014), these had not specifically investigated the association between OCMPs and career growth. For example, Wang et al. (2014) and Nouri and Parker (2013) showed the importance of maintaining fit between employees' career goals and opportunities provided by the organization. Based on the arguments made in these studies, it is hypothesized:

H1: Employees' experiences of OCMPs positively predict their organizational career growth.

Individual career management practices. Individual career management practices include individuals' efforts to achieve their own career goals which may or may not coincide with OCMPs (Garcia 2016; Pandya 2017). It is suggested that when employees are committed to pursue a career instead of simply holding a job, they are more likely to engage in CMPs (Garcia 2016; Van de Griek et al. 2018; Weng and McElroy 2012). Therefore, ICMPs imply an individual's ability to be strategic, readiness for change, ability to identify and access resources, and ability to be pre-occupied with self-improvement. The use of ICMPs may lead to achieve improvements in one's current position and/or move to desired positions within or outside the current employing organization. Individual CMPs involve a wide range of practices. Some of these practices are networking, expertise development, self-nomination, seek information from others, becoming certified, building the individual's brand online, and participating in a mentoring relationship (Garcia 2016; Van de Griek et al. 2018; Wickramasinghe and Jayaweera 2011). Based the on the arguments made above, it is hypothesized:

H2: Employees' experiences of ICMPs positively predict their organizational career growth.

Individual demographic characteristics

The literature suggests that careers are a function of individual efforts and resources (Manzoni et al., 2014), and individual demographic characteristics predict CMPs (e.g., Chen et al. 2016; Van Osch and Schaveling 2017; Wickramasinghe and Jayaweera 2011; Windels and Mallia 2015). We confined to investigate four individual demographic characteristics in this study, namely, age, gender (sex), the level of education attainment, and job position tenure on the use of CMPs. In the current study, we investigated frequently used individual demographic characteristic of job position tenure or the length of an employee's tenure in the

current job from a different angle, i.e., objective measurement of hierarchical career plateau. The literature relating to these are reviewed below.

Age, gender and the level of education attainment. Wickramasinghe and Jayaweera (2011) showed that gender significantly predicts ICMPs, where males undertake more ICMPs than females. Cheramie et al. (2007) and Segers et al. (2008) showed that employees with higher levels of education attainment undertake more ICMPs than their counterparts at lower levels. Although the number of studies that examined these three individual demographic characteristics and career management practices are very limited, based on the arguments made in the above reviewed literature, it is hypothesized for CMPs (inclusive of both OCMPs and ICMPs):

H3: Age, gender and the level of education attainment of employees predict CMPs experienced by them, where age is significantly positively associated with experiencing CMPs, males are experiencing CMPs significantly more than females, and employees with higher levels of educational attainment are experiencing CMPs significantly more than their counterparts at lower levels.

Few previous studies showed that Age, gender and the level of education attainment significantly predict career attitude and growth (Chen et al. 2016; Eby et al. 2005; Manzoni et al. 2014; Okurame 2014; Petersen et al. 2011; Sullivan and Arthur 2006; Windels and Mallia 2015). For instance, Eby et al. (2005) showed that the positive effect of ICMPs on satisfaction with promotion is greater for men than for women. Cheramie et al. (2007) and Segers et al. (2008) showed that employees with higher levels of education attainment pay greater importance to hierarchical promotion than their counterparts at lower levels. Petersen et al. (2011) showed that employees in their younger ages experience rapid career progression. Based on the findings of these studies it is logical to assume that age, gender, and the level of education attainment are associated with employees' perceptions of career growth. Therefore, it is hypothesized:

H4: Age, gender and the level of education attainment of employees predict their organizational career growth, where age is significantly positively associated with experiencing organizational career growth, males are experiencing organizational career growth significantly more than their female counterparts, and employees with higher levels of educational attainment are experiencing organizational career growth more than their counterparts at lower levels.

Hierarchical career plateau- the length of an employee's tenure in the current job.

When career is seen as a hierarchical movement within an organization, hierarchical career plateau is the lack of such a movement (Nachbagauer and Riedl 2002; Shabeer et al. 2019; Xie et al. 2016). Employees, in general, at one time or another reaches a point where further hierarchical advancement is unlikely. However, the concept of hierarchical career plateau stem from the common structure of organizations, i.e. the pyramid (Nachbagauer and Riedl, 2002). Accordingly, hierarchical career plateau is the point at which future career mobility is in reasonable doubt because of the length of time in the present position has been unduly prolonged.

The objective measurement of hierarchical plateau relies on the length of an employee's tenure in the current job (Gould and Penley 1984; Nachbagauer and Riedl 2002; Shabeer et al. 2019; Xie et al. 2016). Previous research provide evidence for the relationship between ICMPs and the length of an employee's tenure in the current job. For example, by defining a plateaued employee as those who have been in their current job for seven or more years, Gould and Penley (1984) showed that hierarchical career plateau predicts the use of ICMPs; and non-plateaued employees reporting a higher use of ICMPs than plateaued employees (p. 248, 259). Wickramasinghe and Jayaweera (2010) also operationalized objective measurement of hierarchical plateau as the length of an employee's tenure in the current job, and showed a direct relationship between hierarchical plateau and ICMPs in Sri Lanka, where employees who were not-plateaued significantly utilize ICMPs. Although none of these studies are conducted in the context of medium-sized organizations, it is logical to assume that due to the fact that medium-sized organizations have limits in expanding their

organizational hierarchy, employees attached to these enterprises may experience hierarchical career plateau. Accordingly, employees may perceive that their further advancement within the current organization is more unlikely and they have to stay in the same position longer than expected. As a result, they may less utilize CMPs with compared to their counterparts who are not-plateaued. Based on the arguments made above, it is hypothesized for CMPs (inclusive of both OCMPs and ICMPs):

H5: Employees who are not hierarchically career plateaued utilize CMPs more than their counterparts whose length of time in the present position has been prolonged (i.e., experiencing hierarchical career plateau).

Few previous studies investigated the relationship between objective measurement of hierarchical career plateau (the length of an employee's tenure in the current job) and employees' career-related attitudes (Allen et al. 1998; Nicholson 1993; Shabeer et al. 2019; Xie et al. 2016). For example, Allen et al. (1998) found evidence for negative work attitudes and the experience of hierarchical plateau. Xie et al. (2016) found a positive relationship between the experience of hierarchical career plateau and turnover intention. Nicholson (1993) did not find a statistically significant relationship between the experience of hierarchical plateau and career satisfaction. Shabeer et al. (2019) found a negative relationship between the perceptions of fit and the experience of hierarchical career plateau. Having considered these findings, it is logical to assume that employees who are not-plateaued may perceive organizational career growth compared to their counterparts who are plateaued. Therefore, it is hypothesized:

H6: Employees who are not hierarchically career plateaued may experience organizational career growth more than their counterparts whose length of time in the present position has been prolonged.

Firm characteristic - the years of business operation

Previous studies identified the importance of the role of the duration of business operation in the adoption of organizational practices (see Cukrowska-Torzewska and Magda 2019). Some studies paid specific attention to SMEs and showed that the adoption of management practices could be affected by the duration of business operation (see Bryson and White 2019; Charles et al. 2015; Karadag 2017; Kilenthong et al. 2016; Lwango et al. 2017; Valtakoski and Witell 2018). In the context of CMPs, Wickramasinghe and Jayaweera (2011) suggested that the duration of business operation could predict the use of CMPs. Based on the literature reviewed above, it is hypothesized:

H7: Firm age (the duration of business operation) positively predicts employees' experiences of CMPs.

When considering the probable relationship between the duration of business operation and organizational career growth, it is hypothesized:

H8: Firm age positively predicts the provision of avenues for employees' organizational career growth.

Small and medium-sized enterprises in Sri Lanka.

In Sri Lanka, enterprises with fewer than 10 employees are identified as micro, those with 10 to 49 employees as small; those with 50 to 99 employees as medium; and those with more than 100 employees as large. The duration of business operation is also a key factor in deciding how systematically enterprises operate in Sri Lanka (Wijetunge 2014). For example, Wijetunge (2014) provided evidence that SMEs with more than seven years of business operation adopted a long term view by actively undertaking some form of business planning. The Federation of Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Sri Lanka (2014) classifies enterprises based on total investment, where enterprises with total investment between 35,000 to 350,000 US Dollars are defined as medium.

In terms of the number of establishments operating in the country, 91.8% of the establishments were micro enterprises, where as 7% were small, 1% were medium and the

balance 0.2% were large enterprises. However, in terms of the number of persons engaged, 44% of persons were engaged in micro enterprises, 18% were in small enterprises, 13% were in medium enterprises, and 25% were in large enterprises (Department of Census and Statistics, 2015). Further, the larger the size of the establishment, the greater the chance that the establishment to be controlled by a male. Accordingly, 26.3%, 8.3%, 6.1% and 4.6% of the enterprises belonging to micro, small-, medium- and large-sized enterprises, respectively, were controlled by females (Department of Census and Statistics, 2015). Fifty per cent of medium-sized and 61% of large-sized enterprises were condensed in urban areas where as 74% of the micro establishments were in rural areas (Department of Census and Statistics, 2015).

Small and medium enterprises face issues in the effective use of physical and human resources due to the lack of proper organization structure, job design and HR planning (Priyanath 2010; Wickramasinghe and Mahmood 2017). First, SMEs are lagging behind in the adoption of proper recruitment and selection procedures (Priyanath 2010). These enterprises seek people who could perform multi-tasks. Second, SMEs face difficulties in attracting people due to their smaller size. Third, even though people are hired, their capabilities need to be enhanced through on-the-job training delivered by existing employees prior to the allocation of job tasks (Wickramasinghe and Mahmood 2017); once new hires' capabilities are enhanced to an acceptable level, they typically leave the workplace for better prospects. As reviewed in the next section on CMPs, Wickramasinghe (2016) found that medium-sized enterprises had adopted formal performance management practices to a certain extent. With regard to SMEs' adherence to government stipulated labor standards, Wickramasinghe and Mahmood (2017) state "due to difficulties in retaining employees, SME owners pay salaries and wages without delay. Some well managed SMEs provide food, accommodation, transport, New Year bonus and had implemented employee recognition schemes, such as Employee of the Month" (p. 403). However, it is very rare to find studies conducted on supervisory or above level employees, who are not an owner, partner, or a member of family of owners/partners of SMEs, like our study.

Methodology

Sample and data collection procedure

Based on the above discussion on SMEs in Sri Lanka, three sample selection criteria were set to identify medium-sized enterprises for the study, i.e., total employee strength should be between 50 to 99; the duration of business operation should be more than seven years as suggested by Wijetunge (2014); total investment should be between 35,000 to 350,000 US Dollars. The Department of Census and Statistics of Sri Lanka provided a list of 105 medium-sized enterprises that fulfilled the selection criteria set for the study. It was decided to collect data covering the entire study population of 105 medium-sized enterprises. Forty-two percent of the enterprises had a dedicated person (a human resource manager) to look after the management of human resources; the remaining 38% managed human resources as part of general management. Of those enterprises that indicated having a human resource manager, twenty percent had a dedicated HRM department/unit.

Two respondent selection criteria were set for the study. First, respondents should occupy a supervisory, executive, or managerial role in the enterprise and should not be an owner, partner or member of the family members of owners/partners. In medium-sized enterprises such a person's contributions towards the performance of the enterprise could be higher and more likely to have expectations of career than owner managers/partners of business as well as other operator, clerical and person's holding low skill jobs with few prospects for career with the enterprise. Second, respondents with at least one year of experience in the current employing enterprise in supervisory or above job positions were considered as potential respondents. This is based on Weng and McElroy's (2012) argument that employees in managerial levels should have at least one year to make an accurate assessment of their organizational career growth. The survey participation was voluntary and anonymous. The submission of completed survey implied reading the description of the study provided as a preamble to the survey, and made a voluntary decision to participate anonymously. The survey questionnaire was distributed covering at least 20% of the employees, who fulfilled the above mentioned selection criteria from each firm, and not more than 10% of employees were selected from the same department/unit. In doing so, no more

than 15 employees were selected from a given enterprise. However, in situations where employees, who fulfilled the above mentioned selection criteria were less than 20% in a particular enterprise, the questionnaire was distributed to the entire population of employees, who qualified to be included in the study. Of the 975 questionnaires distributed covering the 105 enterprises mentioned above, 682 questionnaires were returned within three months, of which 667 were usable, yielding a response rate of 68%.

Descriptive statistics. Descriptive statistics for the characteristics of respondents are shown in Table 1. Of the respondents, 62% had a Bachelor's degree or above educational attainment while remaining 38% had diploma/certificate level qualification or General Certificate in Education after 13 years of schooling; 69% were male; average age was 33 years, and 66% were in the current position for less than seven years. The average duration of business operation of enterprises that respondents came from was 16 years.

Table 1

Measures

Individual career management practices. We used two mechanisms to identify ICMPs that had been implemented by the employees. First, we used prior theoretical and empirical work reviewed earlier to identify ICMPs. Second, parallel to the review of literature, we did a preliminary investigation into ICMPs initiated by employees in medium-sized enterprises in Sri Lanka. Thereafter, the items were first, assessed by a panel of academics and practitioners to ensure the face and content validity. Second, the items were pre-tested with a sample of appropriate employees. The 11-item measure used for the study is given in Appendix 1.

Organizational career management practices. Our intention was to identify employees' perception regarding their exposure to OCMPs that had been implemented by enterprises. We followed the same procedure mentioned above to finalize the item measures. The 10-item measure used for the study is given in Appendix 1.

Organizational career growth. Our intention was to identify employees' perception regarding their level of career growth satisfaction since they had been with their current enterprise. We followed the same procedure mentioned above to finalize the item measures. The 9-item measure used for the study is given in Appendix 1.

Individual demographic characteristics- age, gender and the level of education attainment. Age was measured in years. "Male" was coded as 1 and "female" was coded as 0. The level of education attainment "Bachelor's degree or above" was coded as 1 and "without Bachelor's degree" was coded as 0.

Individual demographic characteristic- job position tenure. Hierarchical career plateau was operationalized as the length of an employee's tenure in the current job. Following Wickramasinghe and Jayaweera's (2010) study conducted in the Sri Lankan context, we considered employees to be in hierarchical career plateau if they had been in their current job for seven years or more. Hierarchical career plateau was coded as not-plateaued (less than 7 years = 1) and plateaued (7 years or more = 0).

Firm characteristic- the duration of business operations. This was measured in years.

Methods of data analysis

Variables were mean centred before computing the product term, although not mathematically required, so as to produce regression coefficients for the variables that would be interpretable within their actual range of values in the data (Hayes 2018). To test common method variance, we used Harman's single-factor test in SPSS; neither single factor emerged from this analysis nor was there a general factor that could account for the majority of variance fulfilling the recommended guidelines of Podsakoff et al., (2003). To confirm this result from SPSS, we further conducted common latent factor test in AMOS, and yielded a similar result suggesting that common method variance is not a concern in our data. Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) were performed. We tested EFA using principle component factor analysis for appropriate (a) internal consistency reliability, (b) factor structure (c) convergent validity, (d) discriminant validity and (e) construct reliability (CR) to identify any issues with multicollinearity and response

bias. We adhered to the criteria stipulated by Hair et al. (2006). As can be seen from Appendix 2, Appendix 3 and Appendix 4, fit indices of ICMPs, OCMPs and organizational career growth revealed good internal consistency reliability, factor structure, convergent validity, discriminant validity and construct reliability. To confirm the factor structures yielded from SPSS, we conducted a series of CFA for item scales of ICMPs, OCMPs and organizational career growth using AMOS, and the summary of results are shown in Table 2.

We used MEDIANTE programme developed by Hayes and Preacher (2011) for testing mediation since this programme accommodates multiple independent variables simultaneously in the mediation model together with multiple mediators in parallel (Hayes and Preacher, 2011). We followed the simple mediation analysis procedure stipulated by Hayes (2018, pages 77-112). Indirect effects were assessed based on 5,000 bootstrapped samples using bias-corrected 95% confidence intervals (CI) for the size and significance of the effects.

Table 2

Results

Principle component factor analysis yielded three components of ICMPs, which were identified as self-presentation, seek guidance, and self-development (refer to Appendix 2). The items of OCMPs converged into a single component (refer to Appendix 3). The two components of organizational career growth were identified as financial rewards and recognition and career goal achievement (refer to Appendix 4). Table 3 provides descriptive statistics and inter-correlations.

Table 3

Table 4 presents the results of mediation analysis. As can be seen in Table 4, OCMPs significantly positively predict organizational career growth in terms of financial rewards and recognition ($B = .462, p < .001$), and career goal achievement ($B = .597, p < .001$) supporting H1. Since all components of ICMPs did not predict all components of organizational career growth H2 is partially supported. Age significantly positively predicts all components of ICMPs - self-presentation ($B = .079, p < .001$), seek guidance ($B = .056, p < .001$), and self-development ($B = .058, p < .001$). However, age does not predict OCMPs. Gender does not predict CMPs. The level of educational attainment significantly predicts self-presentation ($B = .078, p < .05$) and self-development ($B = .107, p < .05$). The results of independent sample t-test shown in Table 5 suggest that employees with a higher level of educational attainment use these practices more than their counterparts at the lower level, and the mean difference is significant. Overall, H3 is partially supported.

Table 4 and Table 5

Age significantly positively predicts career goal achievement ($B = .258, p < .01$) but does not predict financial rewards and recognition. Gender and the level of educational attainment do not predict organizational career growth. Overall, H4 is partially supported. As predicted in H5, hierarchical career plateau significantly predicts all components of ICMPs, namely, self-presentation ($B = .623, p < .001$), seek guidance ($B = .648, p < .001$), and self-development ($B = .407, p < .001$). As shown in Table 5, employees who are not-plateaued use ICMPs more than their counterparts who are plateaued. However, hierarchical career plateau does not predict OCMPs. Overall, H5 is partially supported. Hierarchical career plateau significantly predicts one of the components of organizational career growth, namely, financial rewards and recognition ($B = .427, p < .001$). As shown in Table 5, employees who are not-plateaued perceived more financial rewards and recognition than their counterparts who are plateaued. Since hierarchical career plateau does not predict both components of

organizational career growth, overall, H6 is partially supported. The predictions for H7 and H8 were not supported by the data.

The proposed relationships shown in Figure 1 predicted that CMPs mediate between individual (age, gender, the level of education attainment, and the length of an employee's tenure in the current job termed hierarchical career plateau) and firm (years of business operations) characteristics and organizational career growth. Table 6 is created to depict the associations between the variables that fulfilled the conditions for mediation. When Table 6 is taken together with Table 4, the independent variables of age, the level of education attainment and the experience of hierarchical career plateau significantly predict at least one component of ICMPs. Further, at least one component of ICMPs significantly predicts organizational career growth. However, none of the OCMPs are predicted by age, gender, education, hierarchical career plateau, and the duration of business operation. Further, none of the ICMPs are predicted by gender and the duration of business operation.

Table 6

Discussion

We investigated organization-centred as well as employee-centred antecedents of organizational career growth. The study found that organizational career growth in terms of financial rewards and recognition and career goal achievement were significantly positively predicted by OCMPs. We identified three components of ICMPs namely self-presentation, seek guidance, and self-development. All the components of ICMPs did not significantly predict all the components of organizational career growth, as presented above in Table 4. Further, age is a significant predictor of ICMPs but not OCMPs. The study did not identify gender as a significant predictor of either ICMPs or OCMPs. However, the level of education attainment was found to predict two components of ICMPs, namely self-presentation and self-development; more an individual is educated, the more he/she uses these practices. With regard to the prediction of organizational career growth, age is a significant predictor of

career goal achievement. One of the important findings is that hierarchical career plateau or the length of an employee's tenure in the current job significantly predicts ICMPs. Hierarchical career plateau found to significantly predict organizational career growth in terms of financial rewards and recognition, where employees who are not-plateaued perceive more financial rewards and recognition than their plateaued counterparts. Although the literature emphasizes the importance of organizational career growth, empirical studies linking antecedents of organizational career growth in a mediation relationship are very limited for us to make direct comparisons with our findings. Therefore, the findings of our study have important contributions to theory and implications for practice.

Contribution of the findings for the literature. First, we investigated organizational career growth, for which analysis yielded two component factor structure. Although there are few organizational career growth scales, those are not yet proven for worldwide applicability. We validated our scale in medium-sized enterprises operating in a developing country, Sri Lanka. Our scale consisted of dimensions that evaluated financial rewards, non-financial rewards of recognition as well as the achievement of career goals. The dimensions of financial rewards and career goal achievement were identified as primacy in capturing organizational career growth in previous studies of Kraimer et al. (2011) and Weng et al. (2010). Therefore, the findings of our study support the importance of these dimensions in our study context. However, as mentioned earlier, the scale items that addressed satisfaction with promotion opportunities and opportunities for future promotions were removed due to reliability and validity concerns. This implies the importance of our study context – medium-sized enterprises. We inclined to interpret this situation as employees are aware of the fact that upward movement in the organizational hierarchy is limited, and as a result other dimensions such as recognition became more valid and reliable. Therefore, our scale of organizational career growth is unique since we evaluated its applicability and relevance based on a context-dependent approach.

Second, we investigated ICMPs and OCMPs. In doing so, we made a differentiation between intended and implemented practices by individuals as well as by organizations. This allowed us to isolate practices that are actually implemented and experienced by individuals

reflecting the operational landscape. Further, we collected responses for OCMPs from employees based on their actual experience. This mechanism of data collection yielded better results than gathering information from organizations on the mere presence of OCMPs. Our analysis yielded a single component factor structure for OCMPs. Eby et al. (2005) and Baruch and Peiperl (2000) showed that OCMPs are reflective of a wide range of HRM practices. This is supported by our findings; OCMPs reflected a wide range of practices, such as job posting, succession planning, career paths, training, and performance appraisal to name a few. Hence, our study confirmed associations between OCMPs and individuals' career-related attitude – organizational career growth. This finding implies that when organizations have practices in place to strategically address employees' career needs, they develop favorable attitudes about organizational career growth. We have not come across previous studies that empirically investigated linkages between OCMPs and organizational career growth. As a result, our study implies the importance of future conceptual and empirical work integrating OCMPs and organizational career growth. With regard to ICMPs, analysis yielded a three component factor structure, which were named as self-presentation, seek guidance, and self-development. In terms of explained variation, self-presentation ranked first followed by seek guidance. In other words, these two dimensions explained more variance than self-development initiatives, such as following training programmes and learning new skills. This implies the importance of self-presentation and seek guidance dimensions for the study context.

Third, with regard to individual demographic characteristics as possible predictors of individuals' career attitudes, our findings confirmed the relevance of age in producing significant positive direct effect on organizational career growth. Although previous research suggests the importance of individual demographic characteristics as valuable factors in career attitude and growth (such as Sullivan and Arthur 2006; Okurame 2014), empirical evidence is very rare such as Manzoni et al. 2014 (educational attainment) and Wang et al., 2014 (gender). Therefore, our findings add value to the literature.

Fourth, we approached a frequently used individual demographic characteristic of job position tenure in a different angle, i.e., hierarchical career plateau. The findings of our study

support Wickramasinghe and Jayaweera (2010) that employees, who are not-plateaued are more likely to initiate ICMPs than their counterparts who are plateaued. In other words, when employees are aware of the fact that vertical career movement is limited, they initiate ICMPs prior to experiencing a longer tenure in a job position- hierarchical career plateau. On the one hand, this implies that employees not experiencing hierarchical career plateau are more likely to initiate ICMPs and to ensure a sense of control over their careers and plan their careers. On the other hand, the findings imply that employees who are plateaued in their jobs have to take more control over their careers and need to be committed to pursue a career.

Fifth, the main intention of the study was to test the mediation model proposed in the study. Findings suggested that age, the level of education attainment and the experience of hierarchical career plateau predict organizational career growth through CMPs. Age, the level of education attainment and the experience of hierarchical career plateau showed to have significant mediation relationship with organizational career growth through ICMPs. Therefore, our study provided evidence for the importance of age, the level of education attainment and hierarchical career plateau as antecedents to ICMPs and organizational career growth, in creating a mediating relationship. Since we have not found previous research that tested these relationships, we identify this as one of the main contributions of the study since there is a gap in the career management literature addressing antecedents, and their mediator relationships with organizational career growth.

Sixth, our context of the study, medium-sized enterprises, makes a unique contribution to the literature. We made this restriction on the size of SMEs based on the arguments reviewed in the literature identifying the size of SMEs as an influential factor in the adoption and practice of HRM. In this context, the essential contribution of the present study lies in presenting empirical data on OCMPs as it is *actually* experienced and ICMPs as it is *actually* initiated by employees. Previous research on medium-size enterprises discuss the importance of training and development of employees, such as by Singh and Vohra (2009) and Storey (2002). Still, empirical investigations on career management and career growth of employees of these enterprises were very rare to be found. Therefore, we believe

that we made a novel contribution to the literature on SMEs and HRM practices used to manage employees attached to them.

Seventh, the study contributes to the literature on career management and SME in Sri Lanka, other Asian countries as well as developing countries. First, our findings revealed that employees experienced a range of career management practices. This supports previous studies conducted in Sri Lanka such as Wickramasinghe and Jayaweera (2011) and also in Asia such as Huang et al. (2017), Nawaz and Pangil (2016), Wang et al. (2014) and Singh and Vohra (2009). Second, our findings showed that OCMPs significantly positively predict career growth by way of financial rewards and recognition and career goal achievement. In this regard, Karavardar (2014) in the context of Turkey showed that remuneration growth has strong negative influence on turnover intention; similar observations were also made by Huang et al. (2017), Chen et al. (2016) and Nawaz and Pangil (2016) in the context of Asia. Although these previous studies commented on CMPs and subsequent benefits for individuals, none of these has specifically investigated the association between OCMPs and career growth. Therefore, our findings make novel contributions to the literature on Sri Lanka, other Asian countries and developing countries. Third, with regard to individual demographic characteristics and CMPs, our findings do not support the previous study conducted more than 10 years ago in Sri Lanka by Wickramasinghe and Jayaweera (2011), who found that males undertake more ICMPs than females. Our findings showed that employees with a higher level of educational attainment undertake more CMPs than their counterparts at lower levels. This supports Cheramie et al. (2007) and Segers et al. (2008); however, none of these studies are conducted in the Asian or developing country context. With regard to firm age, our findings do not support the role of firm age on employees' experiencing CMPs and organizational career growth. Although Karadag (2017) and Valtakoski and Witell (2018) showed differences in SMEs by firm age and suggested the importance of adopting growth patterns to suit the same, these studies did not investigate CMPs or career growth of employees. Therefore, the effect of firm age on career management warrant more research to better understand this construct. Fourth, by conceptualizing the length of an employee's tenure in the current job as hierarchical career

plateau, we investigated whether it predicts CMPs. As predicted, we found hierarchical career plateau significantly predicts ICMPs, where non-plateaued employees reporting a higher use than their plateaued counterparts. This finding supports previous findings in the Sri Lankan context by Wickramasinghe and Jayaweera (2010). In the context of the West, Gould and Penley (1984) also showed that employees who are not-plateaued use ICMPs more than their plateaued counterparts. However, we have not found similar studies conducted in SMEs, other Asian countries or developing countries to compare our findings with these contexts. Further, we found that hierarchical career plateau significantly predicts organizational career growth by way of financial rewards and recognition, where non-plateaued employees reporting more financial rewards and recognition than their plateaued counterparts. In this regard, Xie et al. (2016) and Shabeer et al. (2019) in the context of Asia showed negative relationship between hierarchical career plateau and the perceptions of fit. Although these two studies are not directly related to our study, the findings suggest the need of more understanding on the constructs of CMPs, hierarchical career plateau and career growth prospects in organizations. Overall, we identify our study is novel with compared to previous research conducted in the context of Sri Lanka, other Asian countries or other developing countries. On the one hand, although the literature from the West distinguishes enterprises that are small from the medium-sized (see Storey 2002), empirical studies on medium-sized enterprises conducted outside of the West are very rare, and as a result does not provide necessary guidance for decision making. Therefore, the findings presented in this paper adds value to the literature. On the other hand, it is very rare to find empirical studies that are similar in nature to our study on career management. Many research work we cited in this paragraph from Asia and other developing countries did not specifically investigate career management or career growth in medium-sized enterprises or SMEs. The most importantly, our sample was supervisory or above level employees, who are not an owner, partner, or a member of family of owners/partners of medium sized enterprises with 50 to 90 employees. Our findings gave valuable insights on employees' perceptions of being such an employee in these enterprises. Therefore, we provided much needed empirical evidence to an important research area for which very few empirical evidence exists.

Implications for practice. First, OCMPs consist of a wide range of practices leading to attract, motivate and retain employees. Specifically, medium-sized enterprises could be one of the best places to apply these practices, where organizational hierarchy is flatter, enterprises expect employees to be flexible, and each and every individual's contribution is much clearer. Therefore, organizations can plan to offer broad-based career experiences for their employees. In doing so, the provision of OCMPs could play a prominent role. Organizations need to identify the specific practices that are relevant and viable in the enterprises. The results of the factor analysis made us to exclude some important OCMPs such as the provision of in-house training and sponsoring for training outside the organization. The findings imply that the size of the enterprise may have an effect on this managerial decision and such OCMPs may not be much relevant in the study context. Hence, organizations could have an understanding on which kind of OCMPs could enhance employees' attitudes on organizational career growth.

Second, on the one hand, employers are not in a position to manage careers of employees to the benefit of other firms, or perhaps competitors. On the other hand, the findings showed that employees mainly engaged in internally focused ICMPs, which are identified as self-presentation and seek guidance in contrast to externally focused practices that may help them to find jobs elsewhere. The findings suggest that employees, as the sole owners of these practices, could not progress towards achieving expected career outcomes irrespective of how many ICMPs were initiated. Therefore, the findings imply the possibility of identifying OCMPs and internally focused ICMPs as complementary practices, and the importance of sharing the responsibility of career management for the benefit of organizations as well as for employees to create favourable attitudes in organizational career growth.

Third, it is evident during the last few decades that SMEs, in general, have made attempts to move from their short-term focus to be strategic, recruit graduates and actively engage with universities for various needs of their venture start-ups. Medium-sized enterprises can be innovative and flexible in adapting to change due to their size advantage over large enterprises; they can grow at a faster rate than their counterparts of larger

enterprises. Growing SMEs can play a vital role in the internal and external job markets by creating new job opportunities and advancement opportunities for employees. Smaller organizations with compared to larger ones, depend more on employees and expect them to know more, do more, contribute more for the success of the enterprise. Therefore, these enterprises may incline to create favourable perceptions in employees by offering an environment that satisfies their growth needs by adopting OCMPs to a certain extent to be sustainable and competitive.

Conclusion

We presented the findings of the study to support the arguments for the role of five individual and firm characteristics on organizational career growth of employees engaged in medium sized-enterprise. Further, we presented the role of OCMPs, which are planned and implemented by organizations, and ICMPs), which are self-initiated by employees, on organizational career growth. Furthermore, we have shown support for the mediation role of CMPs between age, the level of education attainment and the experience of hierarchical career plateau and organizational career growth (refer to Table 2) of employees engaged in medium sized-enterprises. Through our novel approach we attempted to offer an important new perspective on the CMPs and career growth in Medium-sized enterprises. We believe that debates on the career management and career growth in SMEs can be taken forward through closer articulation of our findings. Therefore, as discussed in the previous sections, the findings of our study have implications for both theory and practice.

Limitations of the study and areas for future research

Activities and actions of organizations and its people cannot be studied without considering their environment. We studied almost homogeneous sample of medium-sized enterprises operating in Sri Lanka. The study relied on self-reported data, and respondents provided not only the ICMPs initiated by them but also their experiences of OCMPs offered to them by enterprises. Future studies could obtain firsthand data from the enterprises on the practices adopted and reasons behind those adoptions. In doing so, specific reference could be made to

understand whether the uncertainties in their business environment make them to choose some practices over others. Future research could also use focus group discussions to examine how and why OCMPs and ICMPs lead to employees' organizational career growth. Such in-depth discussion may provide depth by adding insight and substance to the questionnaire survey. Further, we considered objective measurement of hierarchical plateau that was defined as the length of an employee's tenure in the current job. However, the literature also emphasizes the importance of subjective measurement of hierarchical plateau. Therefore, future research could test it in a moderator relationship when investigating CMPs and career growth. Furthermore, we investigated the effect of the duration of business operation on career management practices and organizational career growth. However, we have not found any significant associations. In addition, future research with large sample size could investigate the combined effect of the duration of business operation and organization size on career management. Our study was confined to medium-sized enterprises only. The medium-sized enterprises in our sample are either operated as family-business or partnerships. Based on the previous studies such as Singh and Vohra (2009), it is possible to assume that the characteristics of entrepreneurs may have an influence on employees' career management. Further, with regard to the formalization of HRM practices, it is possible to assume that when the employee strength increases, the involvement of owner-manager in HRM decisions decreases; the probability of having a dedicated department for HRM increases. Future research could explore this association.

References

- Allen TD, Poteet ML, Russell JEA (1998) Attitudes of managers who are more or less career plateaued. *The Career Development Quarterly* 47: 159-172.
- Ashraf ML (2019) The mediating role of work atmosphere in the relationship between supervisor cooperation, career growth and job satisfaction. *Journal of Workplace Learning* 31: 78-94.
- Bagdadli S, Gianecchini M (2019) Organizational career management practices and objective career success: A systematic review and framework. *Human Resource Management Review* 29: 353-370.

- Baruch Y (1999) Integrated Career systems for the 2000s. *International Journal of Manpower* 20: 432-457.
- Baruch Y (2006) Career development in organizations and beyond: Balancing traditional and contemporary viewpoints. *Human Resource Management Review* 16: 125-138.
- Baruch Y, Peiperl MA (2000) Career management practices: An empirical survey and theoretical implications. *Human Resource Management* 39: 347-366.
- Bryson A, White M (2019) HRM and small-firm employee motivation: Before and after the great recession. *ILR Review* 72:749–773.
- Charles NA, Ojera PB, David O (2015) Factors influencing choice of strategic management modes of small enterprises *Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship* 4:1-22.
- Chen J-Q, Hou Z-J, Li X, Lovelace, KJ, Liu Y-L, Wang, Z-L (2016) The role of career growth in Chinese new employee's turnover process. *Journal of Career Development* 43:11-25.
- Cheramic RA, Sturman MC, Walsh K (2007) Executive career management: Switching organizations and the boundaryless career. *Journal of Vocational Behaviour* 71:359-374.
- Cukrowska-Torzewska E, Magda I (2019) The gender wage gap in the workplace: Does the age of the firm matter?. *European Journal of Industrial Relations*.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0959680118825071>
- Department of Census and Statistics (2015). *Non-agricultural economic activities in Sri Lanka - Economic census 2013/2014*. Colombo, Sri Lanka: Author
- Eby LT, Allen TD, Brinley A (2005) A cross-level investigation of the relationship between career management practices and career-related attitudes. *Group and Organization Management* 30:565-596.
- Federation of Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Sri Lanka (2014) *Entrepreneur of the year Award selection criteria – classification of enterprises*. Colombo, Sri Lanka: Author.
- Garcia EV (2016) Strategic planning: A tool for personal and career growth. *Heart Asia* 8: 36–39. doi:10.1136/heartasia-2015-010684
- Glaser BG (2010) Organizational careers: A forward theory. *The Grounded Theory Review* 9: Retrieved from <http://groundedtheoryreview.com/2010/12/01/organizational-careers-a-forward-theory1/>

- Gould S, Penley LE (1984) Career strategy and salary progression: A study of their relationship in a municipal bureaucracy. *Organizational Behavior and Human Performance* 34:244-265.
- Hair JF Jr, Black WC, Babin BJ, Anderson RE, Tatham RL (2006) *Multivariate Data Analysis*. 6th ed., New Delhi: Pearson.
- Hall DT (2004) The protean career: A quarter-century journey. *Journal of Vocational Behavior* 65: 1-13.
- Hayes AF (2018) *Introduction to mediation, moderation, and conditional process analysis*. New York, NY: The Guilford Press.
- Hayes AF, Preacher KJ (2011) Indirect and direct effects of a multicategorical causal agent in statistical mediation analysis. *Unpublished manuscript, The Ohio State University, Columbus*.
- Huang R-T, Chou TP, Chen C-P (2017) Examining the roles of shared vision and career growth opportunity in developing new employees. *Journal of Organizational Change Management* 30:599-609.
- Johnson S (2002) Lifelong learning and SMEs: Issues for research and policy. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development* 9: 285–295.
- Karadag H (2017) The impact of industry, firm age and education level on financial management performance in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs): Evidence from Turkey. *Journal of Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies* 9:300-314.
- Karavardar G (2014) Organizational career growth and turnover intention: An application in audit firms in Turkey. *International Business Research* 7:67-76.
- Kilenthong P, Hultman CM, Hills GE (2016), Entrepreneurial marketing behaviours: Impact of firm age, firm size and firm's founder. *Journal of Research in Marketing and Entrepreneurship* 18:127-145.
- Kohlmeyer III JM, Parker RJ, Sincich T (2017) Career-related benefits and turnover intentions in accounting firms: The roles of career growth opportunities, trust in superiors, and organizational commitment. In Khondkar E. K. (ed.) *Advances in Accounting Behavioral Research* (Volume 20) Emerald Publishing Limited, pp. 1 - 21.
- Kraimer ML, Seibert SE, Wayne SJ, Liden RC, Bravo J (2011) Antecedents and outcomes of organizational support for development: The critical role of career opportunities. *Journal of Applied Psychology* 96:485–500.

- Lips-Wiersma M, Hall DT (2007) Organizational career development is not dead: A case study on managing the new career during organizational change. *Journal of Organizational Behavior* 28: 771-792.
- Lwango A, Coeurderoy R, Roche GAG (2017) Family influence and SME performance under conditions of firm size and age. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development* 24:629-648.
- Lyness KS, Thompson DE (2000) Climbing the corporate ladder: Do female and male executives follow the same route? *Journal of Applied Psychology* 85:86–101.
- Manzoni A, Härkönen J, Mayer KU (2014) Occupational attainment and career progression - moving on? A growth-curve analysis of occupational attainment and career progression patterns in West Germany. *Social Forces* 92:1285-1312.
- McElroy JC, Weng Q (2016) The connections between careers and organizations in the new career era: Questions answered, questions raised. *Journal of Career Development* 43: 3-10.
- Nachbagauer AGM, Riedl G (2002) Effects of concepts of career plateaus on performance, work satisfaction and commitment. *International Journal of Manpower* 23:716-733.
- Nawaz MS, Pangil F (2016) The relationship between human resource development factors, career growth and turnover intention: The mediating role of organizational commitment. *Management Science Letters* 6:157–176.
- Nicholson N (1993) Purgatory or place of safety? The managerial plateau and organizational age grading. *Human Relations* 46:1369-1389.
- Nouri H, Parker RJ (2013) Career growth opportunities and employee turnover intentions in public accounting firms. *The British Accounting Review* 45: 138–148.
- Okurame DE (2014) Individual factors influencing career growth prospects in contexts of radical organizational changes. *International Business Research* 7:74-87.
- Pandya S (2017) Early success experience as a predictor of fast-track career growth. *Development and Learning in Organizations: An International Journal* 31:10-12.
- Petersen T, Penner A, Hogsnes G (2011) The male marital wage premium: Sorting vs differential pay. *Industrial and Labor Relations Review* 64:283–304.
- Podsakoff P, MacKenzie S, Lee J.-Y, Podsakoff N (2003) Common method biases in behavioral research: A critical review of the literature and recommended remedies. *Journal of Applied Psychology* 88:879-903.

- Priyanath HMS (2010) Managerial deficiencies in the small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Sri Lanka: An empirical evidence of SMEs in Ratnapura District. *Sabaragamuwa University Journal*, 6(1). DOI: 10.4038/suslj.v6i1.1692.
- Razouk AA (2011) High-performance work systems and performance of French small- and medium-sized enterprises: Examining causal order. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management* 22:311-330.
- Reitman F, Schneer JA (2008) Enabling the new careers of the 21st century. *Organization Management Journal* 5:17–28.
- Segers J, Inceoglu L, Vloeberghs D, Bartram D, Henderick E (2008) Protean and boundaryless careers: A study on potential motivators. *Journal of Vocational Behavior* 73:212-230.
- Shabeer S, Mohammed SJ, Jawahar IM, Bilal AR (2019) The mediating influence of fit perceptions in the relationship between career adaptability and job content and hierarchical plateaus. *Journal of Career Development* 46:332–345.
- Singh M, Vohra N (2009) Level of formalisation of human resource management in small and medium enterprises in India. *The Journal of Entrepreneurship* 18:95–116.
- Spagnoli P (2017) Organizational socialization learning, organizational career growth, and work outcomes: A moderated mediation model. *Journal of Career Development* <https://doi.org/10.1177/0894845317700728>
- Spurk D, Hirschi A, Dries N (2019) Antecedents and outcomes of objective versus subjective career success: Competing perspectives and future directions. *Journal of Management* 45: 35-69.
- Storey DJ (2002) Education, training and development policies and practices in medium-sized companies in the UK: Do they really influence firm performance? *Omega* 30:249-264.
- Sullivan SE, Arthur MB (2006) The evolution of the boundaryless career concept: Examining physical and psychological mobility. *Journal of Vocational Behavior* 69:19-29.
- Valtakoski A, Witell L (2018) Service capabilities and servitized SME performance: contingency on firm age. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management* 38:1144-1164.
- Van de Griek OH, Clauson MG, Eby LT (2018) Organizational career growth and proactivity: A typology for individual career development. *Journal of Career Development*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0894845318771216>

- Van Osch Y, Schaveling J (2017) The effects of part-time employment and gender on organizational career growth”, *Journal of Career Development*.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0894845317728359>
- Wang Q, Weng Q, McElroy JC, Ashkanasy NM, Lievens F (2014) Organizational career growth and subsequent voice behavior: The role of affective commitment and gender. *Journal of Vocational Behavior* 84:431–441.
- Weer CH, Greenhaus JH (2017) Managers’ assessments of employees’ organizational career growth opportunities: The role of extra-role performance, work engagement, and perceived organizational commitment. *Journal of Career Development*.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0894845317714892>
- Weng Q, McElroy JC (2012) Organizational career growth, affective occupational commitment and turnover intentions *Journal of Vocational Behavior* 80:256-265.
- Weng Q, McElroy JC, Morrow PC, Liu R (2010) The relationship between career growth and organizational commitment. *Journal of Vocational Behavior* 77:391-400.
- Wickramasinghe V (2016). Performance management in medium-sized enterprises *Performance Improvement Quarterly* 29:1-25
- Wickramasinghe V, Jayaweera M (2010) Impact of career plateau and supervisory support on career satisfaction: A study in offshore outsourced IT firms in Sri Lanka. *Career Development International* 15:544-561.
- Wickramasinghe V, Jayaweera M (2011) Career management strategies among IT professionals in offshore outsourced IT firms in Sri Lanka. *Journal of Management Development* 30:914-926.
- Wickramasinghe V, Mahmood MH (2017) Human Resource Management in Bangladesh and Sri Lanka. In F.L. Cooke and S. Kim (Eds.) *Routledge Handbook of Human Resource Management in Asia*, pp. 392-412, ISBN: 978-1-138-91747-7 (hbk), ISBN: 978-1-315-68900-5 (ebk).
- Wijetunge WADS (2014) Strategic planning practices of manufacturing small and medium scale enterprises in Sri Lanka: An empirical study. *Global Journal of Commerce and Management Perspective* 3:102-109.
- Windels K, Mallia KL (2015) How being female impacts learning and career growth in advertising creative departments. *Employee Relations* 37:122-140.

Xie B, Xin X, Bai G (2016) Hierarchical plateau and turnover intention of employees at the career establishment stage: Examining mediation and moderation effects. *Career Development International* 21:518-533.

Figure and Tables

Figure

Figure 1: Conceptual model

Tables

Table 1: Characteristics of the sample

Gender (%):	
Male	69
Female	31
The highest level of education (%):	
Bachelor's degree or above	62
Without bachelor's degree	38
Age (in yrs):	
Mean	33
S.D.	6
Minimum	22
Maximum	55
Experience of hierarchical career plateau (%):	
In the current position for less than 7 yrs (not plateaued)	66
In the current job position for 7 yrs or more (plateaued)	34
Yrs of business operation of the firm (in yrs):	
Mean	16
S.D.	7
Minimum	4
Maximum	34

Table 2: CFA results for measures of ICMPs, OCMPs and organizational career growth

Measure	χ^2/df	CFI	TLI	RMSEA
3-factor ICMPs	3.964	.852	.815	.038
1-factor OCMPs	4.526	.892	.833	.032
2-factor organizational career growth	4.801	.948	.927	.071

Table 3: Correlations

	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
1 Age	32.91	5.57	-										
2 Gender	-	-	.081	-									
3 Highest level of education	-	-	.174**	.059	-								
4 Hierarchical plateau	-	-	.430**	.066	.093	-							
5 Yrs of business operation	15.51	7.08	.010	.039	.082	.019	-						
6 OCMPs	1.5	1.03	.099	.023	.056	.098	.081	.8					
7 Self-presentation	3.8	.75	.477**	.062	.116*	.412**	.002	.157*	.93				
8 Seek guidance	3.82	.95	.378**	.101	.072	.463**	.002	.159**	.399**	.79			
9 Self-development	2.84	.67	.395**	.028	.137**	.421**	.023	.085	.465**	.466**	.77		
10 Financial rewards and recognition	2.94	.91	.412**	.064	.077	.455**	.035	.361**	.372**	.357**	.403**	.8	.
11 Career goal achievement	2.76	.80	.361**	.033	.086	.311**	.012	.458**	.393**	.324**	.168**	.455**	.8

Notes: *p < 0.05; **p < 0.01; diagonal entries, square root of AVE; off-diagonal entries, correlations between constructs

Table 4: Mediation results

Step 1- X to Y	Financial rewards and recognition		Career goal achievement	
Age	.085(.01)		.258(.01)**	
Gender	.025(.08)		.019(.08)	
Highest level of education	.083(.08)		.049(.08)	
Hierarchical plateau	.427(.12)***		.116(.12)	
Yrs of business operation	.037(.01)		.006(.01)	
R ²	.341***		.145***	
Adj. R ²	.330***		.131***	
Step 2 – X to M	OCM	Self-presentation	Seek guidance	Self-development
Age	.006(.02)	.079(.00)***	.056(.01)***	.058(.00)***
Gender	.038(.13)	.013(.04)	.121(.08)	.050(.05)
Highest level of education	.124(.13)	.078(.04)*	.093(.09)	.107(.05)*
Hierarchical plateau	.193(.19)	.623(.05)***	.648(.13)***	.407(.08)***
Yrs of business operation	.012(.00)	.001(.00)	.000(.00)	.003(.00)
R ²	.021	.835***	.382***	.522***
Adj. R ²	.005	.833***	.372***	.514***
Step 3 - M to Y	Financial rewards and recognition		Career goal achievement	
OCMPs	.462(.03)***		.597(.03)***	
Self-presentation	.066(.06)		.457(.06)***	
Seek guidance	.287(.04)***		.080(.04)	
Self-development	.050(.07)		.270(.06)***	
R ²	.608***		.553***	
Adj. R ²	.604***		.548***	
Step 4 - M to Y after controlling for X	Financial rewards and recognition		Career goal achievement	
Age	.006(.11)		.025(.01)*	
Gender	.004(.07)		.001(.06)	
Highest level of education	.084(.07)		.033(.06)	
Hierarchical plateau	.532(.12)***		.017(.11)	
Yrs of business operation	.000(.00)		.004(.00)	
OCMPs	.385(.03)***		.425(.03)***	
Self-presentation	.159(.11)		.310(.09)**	
Seek guidance	.242(.40)***		.051(.04)	
Self-development	.078(.07)		.319(.06)***	
R ²	.631***		.567***	
Adj. R ²	.621***		.555***	

Note: B(S.E.) are shown, * p < 0.05; ** p < 0.01; *** p < 0.001.

Table 5: Differences by the highest level of education and experience of hierarchical plateau

Variable	By the highest level of education					By experience of hierarchical plateau				
	Without bachelor's degree (coded 0)		Bachelor's degree or above (coded 1)		<i>t</i>	Plateaued (coded 0)		Not-plateaued (coded 1)		<i>t</i>
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.		Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	
Financial rewards and recognition	2.85	.78	2.99	.98	-1.57	2.57	.80	3.66	.67	-13.60***
Career goal achievement	2.67	.71	2.9	.83	-1.73*	2.58	.75	2.70	.75	-1.29
OCMPs	1.42	1.08	1.55	1.15	-1.10	1.42	1.05	1.65	1.15	-1.78
Self-presentation	3.75	.80	3.93	.64	-2.37*	2.96	.54	4.25	.37	-23.89***
Seek guidance	3.90	.91	3.76	.97	1.38	3.06	.89	4.20	.72	-13.11***
Self-development	2.72	.61	2.92	.69	-2.65**	2.54	.54	3.43	.48	-15.24***

Not-plateaued = In the current position for less than 7 yrs

Plateaued = In the current job position for 7 yrs or more

* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$

Table 6. Bootstrapped indirect effects

	B(S.E.)	LL 95% CI	UL 95% CI	Mediation
Age -> Self-presentation -> Career goal achievement	.024(.00)***	.11	.14	Partial
Age -> Self-development -> Career goal achievement	.019(.00)***	.12	.11	Partial
Age -> Seek guidance -> Financial rewards and recognition	.014(.00)***	.11	.18	Full
The highest level of education -> Self-presentation -> Career goal achievement	.024(.01)*	.11	.26	Full
The highest level of education -> Self-development -> Career goal achievement	.034(.02)*	.18	.31	Full
Hierarchical plateau -> Seek guidance -> Financial rewards and recognition	.157(.04)***	.19	.25	Partial
Hierarchical plateau -> Self-presentation -> Career goal achievement	.193(.07)***	.17	.33	Full
Hierarchical plateau -> Self-development -> Career goal achievement	.130(.04)***	.22	.17	Full

Notes: LL = lower limit; CI = confidence interval; UL = upper limit. Unstandardized regression coefficients are reported; standard errors (SE) are in parentheses. Bootstrap sample size = 5,000. * $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.001$ (two-tailed)

Appendix 1: Item measures

Individual career management practices (1 = “very seldom”, 5 = “very often”):

- I seek guidance on things I need to know to get on in this organization
- I ask for guidance from experienced people in the organization
- I look for opportunities to learn new skills within my job scope in the present work
- I look for career related training or qualifications outside the organization
- I ask for feedback on my performance when it was not provided
- I make my superiors aware of my accomplishments
- I assume leadership in work areas where there seems to be no leadership
- I work hard when I know my superiors will appreciate results
- I present myself as a person who “gets things done”
- I make my superiors aware of assignments I am capable of
- I make my superiors aware of my aspirations

Organizational career management practices (1 = “very seldom”, 5 = “very often”):

- My organization uses performance appraisal as a basis for career planning
- A procedure is in place in my organization to address poor performance
- My organization tries to promote “promotion from within” policy as far as possible
- My organization provides an orientation program for all new comers.
- My organization internally advertise vacant jobs
- My organization has job rotation process where applicable
- My organization tries to provide us broad- based work experiences in the organization
- My organization adopts lateral moves to provide cross-functional experience
- I have been given work assignments, which helped me to develop my skills for the future
- My organization applies a performance appraisal procedure

Organizational career growth (1 = “strongly disagree”, 5 = “strongly agree”):

(Cronbach’s alpha = 0.921; KMO sampling adequacy = 0.897; explained total variation = 73)

- I am satisfied with the achievements I have made in my organization towards meeting my career goals
- I am satisfied with the responsibilities I am having in my job towards meeting my career goals
- I am satisfied with the nature of the work I perform in my organization towards meeting my career goals
- I am satisfied with the growth in my monthly salary in my organization
- I am satisfied with financial incentives (such as annual bonus) received from my organization
- I can foresee possibilities of salary growth in years to come
- I have become the best in my area in my organization
- I am satisfied with the recognition I received for my work in my organization
- I have been respected for my contribution by my organization

Appendix 2: Individual career management practices

Item	Self- presentation	Seek guidance	Self- development
I work hard when I know my superiors will appreciate results	.850		
I make my superiors aware of assignments I am capable of	.847		
I assume leadership in work areas where there seems to be no leadership	.796		
I present myself as a person who “gets things done”	.788		
I make my superiors aware of my accomplishments	.765		
I make my superiors aware of my aspirations	.719		
I seek guidance on things I need to know to get on in this organization		.935	
I ask for guidance from experienced people in the organization		.915	
I look for opportunities to learn new skills within my job scope in the present work			.851
I look for career related training or qualifications outside the organization			.828
I ask for feedback on my performance when it was not provided			.703
Explained variation	61.92	12.21	8.96
Cronbach’s alpha	.932	.839	.947
AVE	.64	.86	.63
Construct reliability	.94	.92	.84

Appendix 3: Organizational career management practices

Item	OCM practices
My organization uses performance appraisal as a basis for career planning	.771
A procedure is in place in my organization to address poor performance	.764
My organization tries to promote “promotion from within” policy as far as possible	.742
My organization provides an orientation programme for all new comers	.758
My organization internally advertise vacant jobs	.952
My organization has job rotation process where applicable	.953
My organization tries to provide us broad- based work experiences in the organization	.942
My organization adopts lateral moves to provide cross-functional experience	.957
I have been given work assignments, which helped me to develop my skills for the future	.780
My organization applies a performance appraisal procedure	.768
Explained variation	69.76
Cronbach’s alpha	.946
AVE	.59
Construct reliability	.98

Appendix 4: Organizational career growth

Item	Financial rewards and recognition	Career goal achievement
I am satisfied with financial incentives (such as annual bonus) I am receiving from my organization	.844	
I can foresee possibilities of salary growth in years to come	.838	
I have been respected for my contribution by my organization	.832	
I have become the best in my area in my organization	.778	
I am satisfied with the growth in my monthly salary in my organization	.763	
I am satisfied with the recognition I received for my work in my organization	.755	
I am satisfied with the achievements I have made in my organization towards meeting my career goals		.862
I am satisfied with the responsibilities I am having in my job towards meeting my career goals		.841
I am satisfied with the nature of the work I perform in my organization towards meeting my career goals		.737
Explained variation	.62	.11
Cronbach's alpha	.919	.832
AVE	.64	.64
Construct reliability	.97	.89